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Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Araújo, M. M. de, Santos Jhunior, R. O., Uchôa, M., Mello, A. A. R. & Boaventura, J. M, G. (2025). Distributing value to stakeholders across industries: Influences of power and strategic importance. *Brazilian Administration Review*, 22(3), e240216. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-7692bar2025240216>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Araújo, M. M. de, Santos Jhunior, R. O., Uchôa, M., Mello, A. A. R., Boaventura, J. M, G., Schardong, B. F., & Tonial, G. (2025). Peer review report for: Distributing value to stakeholders across industries: Influences of power and strategic importance. *Brazilian Administration Review*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16615369>

REVIEWERS:

- Bianca Fortes Schardong (Universidade Federal de Santa Maria, Brazil)
- Graciele Tonial (Universidade do Oeste de Santa Catarina, Brazil)

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Bianca Fortes Schardong
Date review returned: January 27, 2025
Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments to the authors

First, I would like to congratulate the authors for addressing a highly relevant topic in the field of corporate governance and stakeholder theory. The article makes an important contribution by investigating how power and strategic importance influence value distribution among stakeholders in different industries, using a solid methodology and data derived from a large, well-grounded sample. However, there are areas that could be improved to strengthen the manuscript and expand its theoretical and practical contributions.

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of reviewers and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited. Only comments that violate the journal's ethical policies such as derogatory or defamatory comments will be edited (omitted) from the report. In these cases, it will be clearly stated that parts of the report were edited. Check [BAR's policies](#).

Although the study extends the work of Boaventura et al. (2020) to the U.S. context, the original theoretical contribution could be more prominently highlighted. Currently, the article focuses on validating previously established hypotheses without delving deeply into the significance of the findings for theoretical advances or market practices. It would be valuable to include a more robust discussion on the theoretical implications, in order to emphasize how the results differ from or complement previous studies. Furthermore, it would be insightful to explore how recent trends, such as digital transformation and ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) demands, might influence the strategic importance and power of stakeholders.

Regarding theoretical contributions, while the article presents relevant data and uses a significant sample, the discussion lacks depth in examining how the findings interact with potential cultural or institutional differences in the U.S. compared to other countries, such as Brazil and Canada. Although the authors indicate this as a topic for future research, addressing it briefly in the discussion section would enrich the text. Even if succinct, such analysis would position the study within a more global perspective, highlighting practical implications that extend beyond the U.S. context and have potential applications in emerging economies and hybrid markets.

The research question is indeed relevant, but its formulation could adopt a more provocative tone, challenging assumptions or theoretical gaps in the existing literature. Rewriting the introduction with a more engaging approach, such as exploring the impacts of the increasing complexity of business environments on power and strategic importance roles, would make the text more appealing and aligned with current demands.

Regarding the abstract, although well-structured, it does not sufficiently emphasize the originality and practical relevance of the findings, which could weaken the manuscript's initial impact. It is recommended to include clear implications for managers and stakeholders, highlighting how the findings can be applied in practice and underscoring the study's contribution to both theoretical and managerial fields.

The sectoral analysis, one of the article's strengths, could also be expanded. The discussion on the significant differences between sectors, such as technology and energy, deserves greater depth. Currently, the text describes sectoral results but does not sufficiently explore the structural reasons behind these variations. Adding practical examples or case studies to explain how specific characteristics of each sector shape dynamics between power and strategic importance would enrich the discussion. For example, the role of environmental regulations in the energy sector or technological interdependence in the software sector are aspects that could be further developed.

In terms of references, while the article relies on a solid theoretical foundation, there is a strong dependence on classical studies, such as Freeman (1984) and Harrison & Bosse (2013). These works are fundamental to the development of stakeholder theory, but including more recent studies could enrich the manuscript and connect it to contemporary discussions. A relevant example is the work of Jones, T. M., Harrison, J. S., & Felps, W. (2018), "How Applying Instrumental Stakeholder Theory Can Provide Sustainable Competitive Advantage," *Academy of Management Review*, 43(3), 371–391. Although this study explores the instrumental stakeholder approach, which is not the primary focus of the article under review, it offers significant contributions by demonstrating how this approach can balance power and strategic importance, contributing to achieving sustainable competitive advantage. Including this reference would strengthen the manuscript's findings and expand its theoretical foundation.

In the same article, Jones, Harrison, and Felps (2018) cite seminal authors such as Peteraf, M. A., and Barney, J. B., who introduced fundamental concepts related to sustainable competitive advantage. Curiously, despite addressing themes that overlap with this discussion, the manuscript under review does not mention these authors or the foundations of competitive advantage theory. Including these theoretical references could strengthen the study's foundation, providing a broader perspective aligned with the core literature on the topic.

Finally, while the article mentions limitations, these are treated superficially. A more in-depth discussion could enhance the study's credibility and pave the way for future research. It would be interesting to explore how the methodological limitations, such as the exclusive focus on IPO prospects, impact the generalizability of the findings and how future studies could address these constraints.

In summary, the article has the potential to make a significant contribution to the field. However, placing greater emphasis on theoretical originality, deepening the sectoral discussion, and including a broader range of contemporary references would strengthen the manuscript's quality, increasing its impact on academic literature and managerial practice. I wish the authors success in implementing the suggested improvements and believe that the study, with the proposed adjustments, can offer even more significant contributions to its research area.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: No

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: No

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).:

Rating:

Interest: Excellent

Quality: Excellent

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 2. Good

Authors' Response

Dear Editor and Esteemed Reviewers,

We express our sincere gratitude for the constructive feedback on our article. Your insights have proven instrumental in refining the quality of our work, and we have diligently incorporated your suggestions to improve the substance of our paper.

For your convenience, we have outlined the changes below.

Best Regards,

The Authors

Editor

C: Based on my reading and the reviewers, we recommend the following improvements:

1) Rewrite the abstract with more precision regarding the results.

2) Theory: The paper could significantly enhance its impact by delving deeper into cultural and institutional differences. As reviewer 1 rightly points out, the study's original contribution to the literature could be further emphasized, highlighting its unique value.

3) Improve the discussion by adding more nuances regarding the industry dynamics and the practical implications;

4) References: It would be beneficial to update the references with recent papers. For instance, there are paragraphs in the introduction that solely cite Freeman, which could be supplemented with more current research

R: Dear Editor, we sincerely appreciate the opportunity to improve our manuscript. All the suggested revisions have been carefully addressed. We believe these enhancements have significantly strengthened the manuscript and look forward to your further evaluation. Thank you for your time and consideration.

Reviewer 1

C: First, I would like to congratulate the authors for addressing a highly relevant topic in the field of corporate governance and stakeholder theory. The article makes an important contribution by investigating how power and strategic importance influence value distribution among stakeholders in different industries, using a solid methodology and data derived from a large, well-grounded sample. However, there are areas that could be improved to strengthen the manuscript and expand its theoretical and practical contributions.

Although the study extends the work of Boaventura et al. (2020) to the U.S. context, the original theoretical contribution could be more prominently highlighted. Currently, the article focuses on validating previously established hypotheses without delving deeply into the significance of the findings for theoretical advances or market practices. It would be valuable to include a more robust discussion on the theoretical implications, in order to emphasize how the results differ from or complement previous studies. Furthermore, it would be insightful to explore how recent trends, such as digital transformation and ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) demands, might influence the strategic importance and power of stakeholders

R: Dear reviewer, thank you for the kind words and insightful feedback. In response, we have sought to highlight more explicitly the previous works that formed the foundation of this study, reinforcing how our findings extend and complement existing research. Additionally, we incorporated reflections on contemporary trends, including ESG demands, drawing on insights from a recently published article (2025). We hope these adjustments clarify the study's theoretical positioning and its relevance to stakeholder management.

C: Regarding theoretical contributions, while the article presents relevant data and uses a significant sample, the discussion lacks depth in examining how the findings interact with potential cultural or institutional differences in the U.S. compared to other countries, such as Brazil and Canada. Although the authors indicate this as a topic for future research, addressing it briefly in the discussion section would enrich the text. Even if succinct, such analysis would position the study within a more global perspective, highlighting practical implications that extend beyond the U.S. context and have potential applications in emerging economies and hybrid markets.

R: Inserted text:

Despite similarities with the Canadian case, which was also studied earlier, insights about the US hold particular importance due to its global representation in the world economy. In sum, after analyzing the results, it can be concluded that strategic importance holds more significance than stakeholder power in the US institutional context when assigning value to stakeholders. This result is in line with the findings of Boaventura et al. (2020) who analyzed Brazil and Araujo et al. (2024) who analyzed Canada, allowing an even greater level of empirical thinking due to the strength of the US market.

Table 9 presents a comparison of results between the 3 countries

C: The research question is indeed relevant, but its formulation could adopt a more provocative tone, challenging assumptions or theoretical gaps in the existing literature. Rewriting the introduction with a more engaging approach, such as exploring the impacts of the increasing complexity of business environments on power and strategic importance roles, would make the text more appealing and aligned with current demands.

R: We revised the introduction to emphasize the increasing complexity of business environments and its implications for stakeholder power and strategic importance. Our new text highlights that universal sustainability pressures (Bello-Pintado et al., 2023) and rising stakeholder diversity require firms to adopt adaptive management strategies (Mahajan et al., 2023) and that multinational enterprises engage stakeholders strategically to enhance corporate social innovation (Saka-Helmhout et al., 2024). Our approach reveals that optimal value creation is achieved through the integrated effect of power and strategic importance, challenging the common assumption that these factors operate independently.

C: Regarding the abstract, although well-structured, it does not sufficiently emphasize the originality and practical relevance of the findings, which could weaken the manuscript's initial impact. It is recommended to include clear implications for managers and stakeholders, highlighting how the findings can be applied in practice and underscoring the study's contribution to both theoretical and managerial fields.

R: In the abstract conclusion, there was already how managers can use the results, however we rewrote it to make it clearer, in addition to making explicit the theoretical contribution of the study when advancing the specificities of the sector.

C: The sectoral analysis, one of the article's strengths, could also be expanded. The discussion on the significant differences between sectors, such as technology and energy, deserves greater depth. Currently, the text describes sectoral results but does not sufficiently explore the structural reasons behind these variations. Adding practical examples or case studies to explain how specific characteristics of each sector shape dynamics between power and strategic importance would enrich the discussion. For example, the role of environmental regulations in the energy sector or technological interdependence in the software sector are aspects that could be further developed.

R: We integrated a new sentence that links the observed differences (e.g., the 81% to 503% ranges) with underlying structural differences in value drivers unique to each industry. For instance, we note that in Manufacturing, value is driven by factors such as alignment of interests and conflict resolution, while in Energy & Transportation and Life Sciences, factors like productive capacity and innovation drive higher strategic importance. This explicit connection (see the paragraph starting with "These variations likely reflect underlying structural differences in the value drivers...") responds directly to the reviewers' request for a more detailed exploration of the reasons behind the sectoral differences

C: In terms of references, while the article relies on a solid theoretical foundation, there is a strong dependence on classical studies, such as Freeman (1984) and Harrison & Bosse (2013). These works are fundamental to the development of stakeholder theory, but including more recent studies could enrich the manuscript and connect it to contemporary discussions. A relevant example is the work of Jones, T. M., Harrison, J. S., & Felps, W. (2018), "How Applying Instrumental Stakeholder Theory Can Provide Sustainable Competitive Advantage," *Academy of Management Review*, 43(3), 371–391. Although this study explores the instrumental stakeholder approach, which is not the primary focus of the article under review, it offers significant contributions by demonstrating how this approach can balance power and strategic importance, contributing to achieving sustainable competitive advantage. Including this reference would strengthen the manuscript's findings and expand its theoretical foundation.

R: We have revised the introduction to integrate recent contributions by Jones, Harrison, & Felps (2018). For example, we now state that instrumental stakeholder theory enables firms to achieve sustainable competitive advantages by cultivating stakeholder relationships characterized by mutual trust and cooperation, thereby balancing power and strategic importance, and enhancing overall firm performance. Our revision emphasizes that this contemporary approach bridges traditional insights

(Freeman, 1984; Harrison & Bosse, 2013) with current trends in stakeholder management.

C: In the same article, Jones, Harrison, and Felps (2018) cite seminal authors such as Peteraf, M. A., and Barney, J. B., who introduced fundamental concepts related to sustainable competitive advantage. Curiously, despite addressing themes that overlap with this discussion, the manuscript under review does not mention these authors or the foundations of competitive advantage theory. Including these theoretical references could strengthen the study's foundation, providing a broader perspective aligned with the core literature on the topic.

R: Dear reviewer, we appreciate your comment. However, after deep reflection and analysis, we decided not to include the studies by Barney and Peteraf. This would prevent different perspectives and views from being included as similar, which could generate discomfort or confusion.

The studies by Barney and Peteraf argue that the competitive advantage of companies comes from their resources and capabilities.

The classic stakeholder theory, developed by Freeman (1984), does not directly address competitive advantage explicitly. It emphasizes that companies should consider the interests and needs of all their stakeholders (and not just shareholders) in order to achieve more responsible, ethical, and sustainable management. Freeman argues that, by satisfying the interests of all relevant stakeholders (customers, employees, suppliers, communities, among others), a company can create long-term value and, therefore, achieve success.

Therefore, by including the two authors mentioned, the study should have focused on one of the following: competitive advantage or resources and capabilities. Which is not the case.

Recently, there has been an improvement in studies that combine RBV with Stakeholder Theory, focusing on competitive advantage. However, in the classical approach, which is the basis of our study, the seminal authors do not adopt such a perspective.

C: Finally, while the article mentions limitations, these are treated superficially. A more in-depth discussion could enhance the study's credibility and pave the way for future research. It would be interesting to explore how the methodological limitations, such as the exclusive focus on IPO prospects, impact the generalizability of the findings and how future studies could address these constraints.

R: Thank you for the comment. We did our best to address this point by expanding the discussion on limitations, particularly regarding the exclusive focus on IPO prospectuses and its impact on the generalizability of the findings. We also suggested future research directions to address these constraints. These adjustments were made while balancing other reviewers' suggestions and adhering to the journal's word limit.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Graciele Tonial

Date review returned: February 13, 2025

Recommendation: Minor revision

Dear Author(s):

It is believed that the research contributes to the advancement of discussions on Stakeholder theory and its relationship with the influence of power and strategic importance.

However, for publication, the following adjustments are suggested:

In the abstract section:

The results are presented in a general and overly broad manner, which diminishes their impact. To clearly highlight the contribution of the research to the state of the art, it is essential to present the findings with greater specificity and concreteness. This will highlight the novelty and significance of the work and also provide readers with a clear understanding of how the study advances knowledge in the field.

Introduction Section:

In the first 3 paragraphs, it is suggested to enhance the discussion on the topic with research by other authors, for example, not only citing Freeman et al., who I understand to be the seminal author, but other authors discuss and support the current theoretical advances. Therefore, it is recommended to include 2 or 3 authors who discuss and expand the understanding of the topic.

Likewise, in the 4th paragraph, it is recommended to include current authors who corroborate or disagree with the discussion presented in the article, to better support the research.

In paragraph 8, p. 3, line 59, . Although the studies have explored it is suggested to add which studies. This reinforces the importance of the research.

In the last paragraph, it is suggested to expand the statements of the theoretical and practical contribution of the paper. It would be appropriate to better justify the contribution.

In section 2, which addresses Theory, it is understood that the author(s) present the theoretical support for the research hypotheses. Being well-articulated and structured, effectively presenting the thematic categories in detail.

Methodology section

The author(s) justify the choice of the sample in a clear and timely manner, but it is recommended to include the justification with an author from the statistical area, to support the delimitation of the sample number, which validation for this number of companies was adopted? It is not clear in the text.

It is suggested to include authors who support the choices for the statistical techniques used.

For example, which author supports and sustains the use of the NVivo software, for content analysis, it is recommended to justify.

It is recommended to make it clearer how NVivo was used, which version was used?

It is also recommended to cite an author who supports and recommends the use of the OLS regression technique.

Results section.

It is recommended to present the practical implications in the results, because although the theoretical insights are strong, the practical implications for managers, CEOs, directors, in their decision-making. Adding specific examples would help bridge the gap between theory and practice, making the work more applicable in real-world contexts.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: No

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable).

Rating:

Interest: Excellent

Quality: Good

Originality: Good

Overall: Good

Authors' Response

C: The results are presented in a general and overly broad manner, which diminishes their impact. To clearly highlight the contribution of the research to the state of the art, it is essential to present the findings with greater specificity and concreteness. This will highlight the novelty and significance of the work and also provide readers with a clear understanding of how the study advances knowledge in the field.

R: We have integrated specific numerical ranges (e.g., 81% in Manufacturing, 254% in Energy & Transportation, 503% in Life Sciences) and provided concrete examples that illustrate the differences in value drivers between sectors. These details make our results more precise and substantiate our claims with specific empirical data, thereby enhancing the overall impact of our findings.

C: In the first 3 paragraphs, it is suggested to enhance the discussion on the topic with research by other authors, for example, not only citing Freeman et al., who I understand to be the seminal author, but other authors discuss and support the current theoretical advances. Therefore, it is recommended to include 2 or 3 authors who discuss and expand the understanding of the topic.

Likewise, in the 4th paragraph, it is recommended to include current authors who corroborate or disagree with the discussion presented in the article, to better support the research.

In paragraph 8, p. 3, line 59, "Although the studies have explored....." it is suggested to add which studies. This reinforces the importance of the research.

R: We have revised the introduction to incorporate additional contemporary research. In the first three paragraphs, we now reference not only Freeman et al. but also include Valentinov & Roth (2024), Jones, Harrison, & Felps (2018), Bello-Pintado et al. (2023), and Mahajan et al. (2023) to expand the theoretical discussion on stakeholder relationships and adaptive management strategies. In the fourth (now fifth) paragraph, we now specify that previous studies exploring the link between stakeholder power, strategic importance, and value distribution include Boaventura et al. (2020) and Araujo et al. (2024).

C: In the last paragraph (introduction), it is suggested to expand the statements of the theoretical and practical contribution of the paper. It would be appropriate to better justify the contribution.

R: Inserted text:

By extending previous research on stakeholder value distribution, this study provides a novel perspective on the interplay between power and strategic importance in firms operating within a Liberal Market Economy. Unlike prior studies focusing on specific national contexts, our research captures a broader economic environment where market mechanisms drive corporate decisions. This contribution is particularly relevant for managers and policymakers, as it offers insights into how firms prioritize stakeholders based on their strategic roles. Additionally, the study's industry-level analysis underscores key sectoral differences, equipping practitioners with actionable knowledge to enhance stakeholder engagement strategies across different industries.

C: 1. The author(s) justify the choice of the sample in a clear and timely manner, but it is recommended to include the justification with an author from the statistical area, to support the delimitation of the sample number. Which validation for this number of companies was adopted? It is not clear in the text.

2. It is suggested to include authors who support the choices for the statistical techniques used.

For example, which author supports and sustains the use of the NVivo software for content analysis? It is recommended to justify.

It is recommended to make it clearer how NVivo was used, which version was used?

3. It is also recommended to cite an author who supports and recommends the use of the OLS regression technique.

R: Dear reviewer, to support the methodological choices, we have included the following authors and studies

1. We included the Hair reference to justify the sample size

2. Added justification based on Creswell, in addition to the justifications based on Bardin (1977) and the study by Boaventura (2019) that were already included in the article.

3. OLS based on Hair et al. (2014)

C: It is recommended to present the practical implications in the results, because although the theoretical insights are strong, the practical implications for managers, CEOs, directors, in their decision-making. Adding specific examples would help bridge the gap between theory and practice, making the work more applicable in real-world contexts.

R: We added a paragraph that explicitly translates our empirical findings into practical recommendations.

For example, in the technology sector, we advise that firms should prioritize stakeholders such as software developers and communication operators (whose value drivers include continuous improvement and robust technological infrastructure), while in Manufacturing, the focus should be on operational efficiency and process reliability. This guidance (see the paragraph beginning with "From a practical perspective, these results provide managers with clear guidance..") directly addresses the feedback by bridging theoretical insights with actionable strategies for decision-makers.

Reviewer 3 report

Reviewer 3 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 3 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Bianca Fortes Schardong
Date review returned: March 30, 2025
Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the authors

Dear Authors,

I would like to congratulate you on your work in revising the manuscript. Your responses were precise, and the modifications significantly improved the clarity, theoretical depth, and practical relevance of the study. The way you have addressed the suggestions has further strengthened the impact of your article in the field of corporate governance and stakeholder theory.

Best regards,

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable).:

Rating:

Interest: Excellent

Quality: Excellent

Originality: Excellent

Overall: Excellent

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Graciele Toniel

Date review returned: April 29, 2025

Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the authors

Dear Author(s)

After reviewing the paper again, I realized that the requested revisions were met.

I highlight the revised text in the abstract and in the introduction section.

Adjustments were also made to the methodology section, so that authors who support the methodological choices and paths followed are cited.

I also highlight that the adjustments requested in the discussion and final considerations were carried out accordingly.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable):

Rating:

Interest: Good

Quality: Good

Originality: Good

Overall: Good

Reviewer 3 report

Reviewer 3 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

There was no reviewer's evaluation for this round. For this reason, there is no authors' response.